

THE NEXUS BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM KEBRI BEYAH CITY PUBLIC SECTOR ORGANIZATIONS, ETHIOPIA

*Dr. Tazebachew Achenef Alem¹,
Assistance Professor,
Department of Management,
Jigjiga University, Ethiopia*

Aschalew Mulugeta (Asst. Professor)²

*Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Commerce and
Management Studies, College of Arts and Commerce, Andhra
University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.*

Dr. Biruk Ayalew Wondim³

Associate Professor

Department of Accounting and Finance

Kampala International University, Uganda

*Corresponding Author
Aschalew Mulugeta*

Abstract

This study aimed to address the effect of emotional intelligence on employee's performance in Kebri Beyah public sectors. The study used descriptive and explanatory research designs with quantitative approach. Stratified random sampling techniques were employed and data were collected by structured questionnaires. The independent variables are the four domains of emotional intelligence and the dependent variable is employee's performance. The data were analyzed using inferential statistics and the data analysis showed that all the four domains of emotional intelligence had significant effect on employee's performance. Overall, the results revealed that all independent variables accounted for 89.9% of the variance in employees' performance ($R^2 = 0.899$). Relationship management was found to be the dominant domain to be well ranked by the respondents. It is also recommended that organizations need to consider emotional intelligence during the recruitment and selection process of employees. They also need to develop periodic monitoring and evaluation system of their employees' emotional intelligence along with regular training and development programs. Finally, employees are recommended to update themselves on the skill of emotional intelligence.

Key words: Emotional, Intelligence, Employees' Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Emotional intelligence (EI) has reaped considerable scholarly attention, yet there remains no universally accepted definition. Various researchers have proposed distinct yet overlapping conceptualizations of emotional intelligence, emphasizing its multifaceted nature. It involves being aware of one's feelings as well as identifying and effectively regulating those of others (Sukor et al., (2023). In his up-to-date publish, Goleman (2004) defines emotional intelligence as a skill set through which individuals exert control over their lives via self-awareness, improve their functioning through self-management, and understand the emotional dynamics of interpersonal relationships. Sternberg (1997) also contributes to this discourse, theorizing emotional intelligence as an individual's capacity to perceive, comprehend, and regulate emotions in one and others that affect employees' performance. These competencies significantly influence an individual's capacity to regulate moods and impulses, ultimately enhancing workplace performance and efficiency." It show how both construct related each other.

Whereas employee performance can be understood as the successful execution of assigned duties using available resources, aiming to meet predefined standards (Akhtar et al., 2017). It encompasses both observable behaviors and internal cognitive processes such as reasoning, planning, decision-making, and problem-solving. Performance is influenced by various factors, including an individual's knowledge, skills, capabilities, and motivational levels (Oladep & Gunu, 2014).

In contemporary organizational contexts, emotional intelligence has emerged as a critical factor influencing performance. Individuals with high emotional intelligence tend to exhibit better self-awareness and emotion regulation, enabling them to interpret their emotional states and those of others effectively. This emotional insight contributes to enhanced interpersonal understanding, conflict resolution, and resilience in the face of challenges, ultimately supporting superior job performance Alferaih, (2021).

2. Rational of the Study

Currently, public sector in Ethiopia is not fully bonded by intense competition one with the other as owned by the government even the way serve the community is not as such interesting which harm negatively its performances. The overall performance of the sector in Ethiopia in general and the public in particular is not showing improvements in its job performance though the implementation of BPR, balanced scorecards and now kaizen (performance management system (reports of Human Resource Management Bureau, 2011) and Kassa (2022). So what make it to happen might relate to emotional intelligence level of understanding. However, surveys conducted by Moges (2022) and Radu (2023) regarding employees performance showed the following findings such as, some staffs faced with lack of self-awareness, social awareness, self-management and relationship management that can enhance job

performances. He added lack of enthusiasm to help clients by some staffs that he/she feels annoying and unfriendly approach due to their improper management of their emotional intelligence .

The researcher wish to bridge the gaps identified in this study by putting more emphasis and focus on emotional intelligence (self-awareness, social awareness, self-management and relationship management) play towards the improvement of employees' performance in public sector organizations Ayele (2015). Primarily by doing the foundational work of determining where we are and where we need to go, leaving aside the how, for further research. Moreover, few authors have had little studies in this area of emotional intelligence on employee performance in public service organizations limited in Addis Ababa Mahilet (2018) and Tsedey (2015).

Again the existing body of research on emotional intelligence predominantly focuses on specific dimensions or utilizes self-reported instruments, which may not accurately reflect actual levels of this part. Furthermore, many of these studies are situated within Western contexts, rendering their applicability to developing nations, such as Ethiopia, somewhat constrained Deshwal (2016), Munir and Azam (2017) and Mujanah (2019). Nasrul & Alfalah, (2020) explored the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee performance. However, their work was primarily theoretical, drawing upon secondary data from prior studies conducted predominantly in European and American contexts. As a result, their findings lack empirical grounding and do not adequately reflect the socio-cultural and organizational realities of developing countries Meheret (2015). Therefore, the researcher viewed that the results found by different researchers on the effect of emotional intelligence on employee performance are different. This showed that there is a theory inconsistency as studies were made by different researchers as expressed above Assefa (2021), Chughtai and Lattef (2015), Serhan and Gazzaz (2019).

The study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- To investigate the effect of emotional intelligence on employee's performance the case of Kebri Beyah city public sectors organizations.

2.1.Literature Review

2.1.1. Theoretical and empirical literatures

There are three theoretical approaches of EI models: the EI skill based model, Reuven Bar-On's Emotional-Social Intelligence (ESI) model (Bar-On, 2006), and the Emotional Competencies model focused on the workplace (Yordanos, 2018). Peter Salovey and John Mayer first proposed their theory of emotional Intelligence in 1990. Their theory framed emotional Intelligence within a model of intelligence (Mayer & Salovey, 2000). Bar-On (1997) has placed emotional Intelligence in the context of personality theory, specifically a model of well-being. Goleman on the other hand formulated emotional Intelligence

in terms of a theory of performance. Thorndike (1920) was among the first to introduce the notion of "social intelligence," which he defined as the capacity to manage and understand human interactions effectively. This laid the groundwork for subsequent theoretical advancements.

Goleman (2006) later emphasized its practical significance, arguing that emotional intelligence plays a critical role in achieving success in various life domains, particularly in occupational settings. In contrast, Bar-On (1988,) conceptualized emotional intelligence as an array of interrelated emotional and social competencies and skills that influence one's ability to cope effectively with environmental demands. His model integrates aspects of personality and general well-being.

Despite these differing emphases, the models share foundational components. emotional intelligence broadly refers to the capacity to recognize, understand, manage, and utilize emotions in oneself and others. Core domains typically include self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management (Priyam & Tanu, 2016). While all three models contribute to a comprehensive understanding of emotional intelligence, Goleman's performance-oriented approach offers particularly practical applications for organizational settings, enabling better identification and development of high-performing employees. Goleman's (2001) model of emotional intelligence presents emotional intelligence as a composite of competencies and skills that influence leadership and performance. His mixed model, derived from both ability and personality traits, encompasses four core domains: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management. Each domain is associated with specific competencies such as emotional self-awareness, empathy, and conflict management.

2.1.2. Emotional Intelligence and Employee Performance

Employees with high emotional intelligence demonstrate superior emotional regulation, adaptability, and interpersonal effectiveness, contributing to better performance outcomes across various roles (Rastogi & Sharma, 2022).

Emotional Intelligence has been identified as a key factor in facilitating these interactions and enhancing job performance. Employees with high emotional intelligence are better equipped to regulate their emotions, understand others' emotional states, and respond appropriately in varying workplace scenarios (Neerupa & Srinivas, 2019). These competencies often translate into improved teamwork, customer relations, and conflict resolution.

The literature underscores the pivotal role of EI in enhancing subjective well-being, social connectedness, and professional success. Conversely, deficits in emotional intelligence are associated with negative affective states and reduced workplace efficacy. Although existing studies affirm the link between emotional intelligence and job performance, gaps remain concerning the mechanisms through which this relationship manifests and how contextual variables moderate its effects Alismail et al., (2022). This review identifies the need for further empirical exploration into the evolving influence of emotional

intelligence on employee behavior and organizational outcomes. Specifically, it calls for a multidimensional examination of emotional competencies in relation to performance metrics, employee engagement, and organizational support systems.

2.1.3. Empirical Literature Review

Several studies have indicated a strong, positive correlation between emotional intelligence and employee performance, suggesting a unidirectional relationship in which increases in emotional intelligence predict enhancements in performance outcomes. Additionally, constructs such as organizational support, communication, and self-efficacy have been identified as key contributors to this relationship (Gong et al., 2019).

Davis (2019), in a peer-reviewed study conducted in the United States, concluded that EI positively influences employee morale, retention, occupational stress, and overall job performance. In India, Priyam and Tanu (2016) explored the impact of emotional intelligence on IT employees, reporting that EI accounted for a 31.9% variation in men's performance and 26.7% in women's. This gendered analysis highlighted the nuanced effects of EI across different employee groups.

Dayo & Sunday (2012), the study on the impact of emotional intelligence on workers' behavior in industrial organizations in Nigeria has shown that there was a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and workers' job performance. Emotional intelligence had a significant positive relationship with job performance, $r = 0.241$, $p < 0.001$.

Akhtar et al. (2017) extended these findings in a study from Islamabad, emphasizing the moderating role of perceived organizational support. Their research demonstrated that the relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance is amplified when employees perceive strong organizational backing. Similarly, Yang et al., (2020), through a comprehensive literature review, reinforced that emotional intelligence competencies enhance job performance and emotional regulation in the workplace.

In the Ethiopia context, a few scholars have tried to investigate the effect of emotional intelligence on employee performance contribution in different sectors, Ayele (2015) and Kassa (2022), have reassured that emotional intelligence indeed has a vital contribution in enhancing employee performance in the Ethiopian public sector, the significance of emotional intelligence on employee performance cannot be overstated, as highlighted by studies conducted by Yohannes and lemma (2021) and Desta (2020).

2.3. Conceptual Framework

Goleman's (2001) model of emotional intelligence presents EI as a composite of competencies and skills that influence leadership and performance. His mixed model, derived from both ability and personality traits, encompasses four core domains: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management. Priyam & Tanu (2017) prepared a tool to measure employee's performance and included in the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Source: adapted from Alamzeb (2023) and Salovey and Mayer (2007)

3. Research Methodology and Design

The study was explanatory research design to achieve the expected objectives of the research.

According to Kothari, (2004) a research approach brings to simplify the fact there are two basic approaches these are quantitative and qualitative approach, if both they are mixed. A quantitative data can provide a more complete picture of the effect of reward system and employee performance. Therefore, the researcher used the mixed method research approach to show and explain the result how it was obtained.

3.1. Population and Sample Size

The total population of the research is 649 employees of currently existing in the study area.

In this study to make the sample more representatives, the sample size of the study was determined using the formula adopted by Yamane (1967). Thus, the formula used to calculate the sample size is:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where:

n= the desired sample size

N= the population size 95% confidence level;

e= the level of significance error, at 0.05

This formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{649}{1 + 649(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 649$$

The calculated sample size (n) of 248 members from the target population of 649 was selected for the study.

Based on the above sample the formula n/N was applied to determine each office or bureau to distribute proportionally. Therefore, $248/649=0.38$

Table 1. Summary of the target population and sample size

No	Name of the Sectors	Proportion	Sample
1	City Council	14*0.38	5
2	City Security and Militia Office	31*0.38	12
3	Corporate Promotion Office	27*0.38	10
4	Education Office	167*0.38	63
5	Health Office	27*0.38	10
6	Mayor Office	27*0.38	10
7	Micro And Small Enterprise Agency	25*0.38	10
8	Office Of Finance And Economic Development	20*0.38	8
9	Office Of Kebele Administration	55*0.38	21
10	Office Of City Service	30*0.38	12
11	Public Service And Human Resource Department Office	28*0.38	11
12	Revenue Office	79*0.38	31
13	Sanitation And Beatification	24*0.38	9
14	Justice And Prosecutor Bureau	11*0.38	5
15	Sport Office	10*0.38	4
16	Trade, Industry And Urban Development	31*0.38	12
17	Water Resource	22*0.38	8
18	Women Affaire Office	9*0.38	3
19	Communication Office	12*0.38	4
	Total	649*0.38	248

Source, Kebri Beyah civil service bureau, 2025

The researcher used simple random sampling technique for questionnaires to obtain primary data or information from employees by selectin the sectors judgmentally.

3.2. Measurement of variables and Data Analysis Techniques

Close ended questionnaire contains items of Likert scale type which range from one strongly disagree to five strongly agree as a measuring instrument. Secondary data was collected from different supportive sources to the study Creswell (2012). It was used literature and documents -`such as previous studies, books, reports, proclamation, manuals, journals and internet sources were applicable.

Multiple regression attempts to model the relationship between two or more explanatory variables and a response variable by fitting a linear equation to observed data. Every value of the independent variable x was associated with a value of the dependent variable y. The multiple regression formula we adopted for this study was made on the independent variables and dependent variable as below.

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + e$$

Where: Y_1 = dependent variables (employees performance)

(X_2 = self-awareness, X_2 = self-management, X_3 = social-awareness, and X_4 = relationship management)

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4,$ = the coefficients of the variables, e = the error term

β_0 was a constant while is the error term in the function.

3.3. Discussion of findings

Table 2 below shows the means and standard deviations of emotional intelligence variables such as awareness, self-management, social-awareness, and relationship management rated by respondents.

Table 2. Mean value of variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Awareness	2.0275	0.4387
Self-management	2.1643	0.6987
Social-awareness	2.4162	0.5801
Relationship management	3.0418	0.7098
Valid N (list wise)		

Source: Own survey, 2025

As we can see in table 2 relatively better mean result for relationship management was found ($M = 3.04$, $SD = 0.70$). Social awareness ($M=2.41$, $SD=0.58$), self-management ($M = 2.16$, $SD = 0.69$), and self-awareness ($M = 2.02$, $SD = 0.43$) were scored as mean value. From this we can observe that among those predictors of emotional intelligence relationship management is relatively has acceptable mean results than others that have mean value of below the average of five Likert scale which implies the employees are not working well as per the explained variables.

Whereas multiple regression analysis was employed to examine the effect of emotional intelligence on employees' performance. The result also helps us to understand which variables among the five independent variables are more determine of outcome variable. The findings further indicate model summary result, ANOVA and coefficient of multiple regressions consecutively. Actually before the study run the regression all the multiple regression assumptions such as (normality, linearity, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity) were tested and satisfied the requirements.

Table 3: Model Summary of multiple regressions

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.948 ^a	.899	.896		1.576	.430

a. Predictors: (Constant), self-awareness, self-management, social-awareness, relationship management

As shown depicted in the above table 3 there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between independent and dependent variables. In overall, the results revealed that all independent variables accounted for 89.9% of the variance in employees' performance ($R^2 = 0.899$). Thus, 89.9% of the variation of employees' performance can be explained by the four emotional intelligence dimensions questions and other variables that didn't used here could explain the variation in employees' performance is 10.1 percent

Table 4: ANOVA analysis

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4886.361	5	977.272	393.491	<.001 ^b
	Residual	551.358	222	2.484		
	Total	5437.719	227			

a. Dependent Variable: employees' performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), self-awareness, self-management, social-awareness, relationship management

The result in the ANOVA table confirmed the significance of the overall model by p -value of < 0.001 which is below the alpha level, i.e. 0.05, which means, the independent variables taken together have statistically significant relationship with the dependent variable under study.

Table 5: Coefficient value of multiple regression analysis

Model	Unstandardized coefficient	Standard error	Standardized coefficient	t	Sig.
Constant	.867	.392		2.211	.028
Awareness	.280	.096	.207	2.910	.004
Self-management	.201	.096	.155	2.093	.037
Social-awareness	.255	.116	.179	2.194	.029
Relationship management	.325	.135	.223	2.410	.017

Source; survey data 2025

All the components of emotional intelligence (awareness, self-management, social-awareness, relationship management) do have significant effects on employees performance at $P < .05$ significance level. The results of multiple regressions, as presented in Table 5 above, revealed that relationship management had a positive and significant effect on employees' performance with values ($\beta=0.325$, $t=2.41$, $p = <0.001$). This indicates the unstandardized coefficient value of each independent variable shown that, a unit change in by keeping the other variables constant, its employees' performance would increase by 32.5%. Therefore, relationship management components of the predictor had a positive and significant effect on the outcome variable at 95% confidence level and the finding is highly supported by Misganaw (2021). The regression finding also showed the positive and significant effect of social-awareness on employees' performance with values ($\beta=0.255$, $t = 2.194$, $p = <0.001$). This indicates the unstandardized coefficient value of each independent variable shown that, a unit change in by keeping the other variables constant, its employees' performance would increase by 25.5%. Therefore, social-awareness components of the independent variable had a positive and significant effect on dependent variable at 95% confidence level. Chughtai and Lateef (2015) findings supported this study results.

As shown in the same table self-management had a positive and significant effect on the criterion variable with values ($\beta=0.201$, $t = 2.093$, $p = < 0.001$). This indicates the unstandardized coefficient value of each independent variable shown that, a unit change in by keeping the other variables constant, employees' performance would increase by 20.1%. Therefore, self-management as a component had a positive and significant effect on criterion variable at 95% confidence level. Finds of Kassa (2022), Yang et al. (2020), and Johar et al. (2023) had also a positive significant effect on self-management that supports this study output. At the same time awareness had a positive and significant effect on the dependent variable with values ($\beta=0.004$, $t = 0.280$, $p = 2.910$). This indicates a unit change in this variable; its outcome variable would increase by 28%. This result is highly related with the findings of Iswantir et al. (2023), Obaide (2022). However, the finding of Sukor et al. (2023) is inconsistent with this research result.

4. Conclusions

The main objective of this research was to examine the effect of emotional intelligence on employees' performance the case of public sector organization in Kebri Beyah city. The analysis confirmed that all explanatory variables have the mean value of below average. This implies that employees attitude towards the emotional intelligence in the sector is not as such expected. In addition to this mean value the outcome variable shows that the level of employees' performance in the study area is low.

In conclusion, when the four domains of emotional intelligence were measured by Likert scale, relationship management was found to be the dominant domain to be well ranked by the respondents. All had a positive and significant relationship between the four domains of emotional intelligence and employee's performance. Based on the multiple regression analysis of the study, 89.6% of employee's performance can be predicted and explained by the four domains of emotional intelligence. Which implies that 10.4% of variation of employees' performance is explained by other variables not used here. Of the four domains of emotional intelligence, relationship management and social-awareness were found to have comparably 32.5 and 25.5% positive effect respectively and self-management and self-awareness had 20.1% and 28.0% comparable positive effect on employee's performance respectively. The entire research pointed out that all the domains of emotional intelligence had positive effect on employee's performance.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on this fact and the findings of this study the following recommendations are proposed to help improve the job performances of employees' in Kebri Beyah city Public sector organization using emotional intelligence as a determinant factor.

- The city administration should actively seek input information on employees' emotional intelligence from its community, including who get service in the public sector directly or indirectly and other stakeholders working with them such as NGOs. This could involve creating a community advisory board holding regular meetings with leaders and employees' to discuss the policies and procedures, and also it involves to create a system for employees to give feedback on their performance, and this feedback should be used to help employees improve their performance using their awareness, self-management, social management and social awareness.
- Employees' should be open to the public and being responsible and accountability through establishing a system for collecting community complaints and suggestions to ensure that problems are addressed in a timely and effective manner for the behavior works portray as emotional intelligence.
- The company should prioritize the integration of emotional intelligence (EI) into the workplace as a key factor in enhancing employee performance and overall organizational productivity. All employees must understand the importance of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management in their daily tasks. To support this, the organization should establish an environment where emotional intelligence is considered an essential part of every employee's role. This can be achieved by implementing continuous training and capacity-building programs focused on improving emotional intelligence skills.

- These programs should include practical guidance on managing client interactions, maintaining accurate records, and fostering effective communication among team members. Additionally, the company should give greater consideration to all emotional dimensions that positively influence employee performance, as identified in recent studies. Emphasizing these elements will help build a more engaged, resilient, and high-performing workforce.

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